

GOODBYE PARTY FOR MISS PUSHPA T.S: A PARODY

Prof. Tagad Bhushan Vitthal.

Mahatma Phule Nutan Mahavidyalaya Mirajgaon.

Tal:- Karjat. Dist:- Ahmednagar.

Pin:-414401.

Abstract:-

This paper focuses light on the use of present progressive tense instead of simple present tense, ironical situations, literal translation, Babu English by Nissim Ezekiel in the poem 'Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa T.S'. This poem includes in "Hymns and Darkness" is one of Ezekiel's very Indian Poems in Indian English. The poem is a hilarious parody of and biting satire on the idiolectical features of English spoken by people from Gujarat. The paper gives close attention on common Indian use of the present progressive.

Keywords:-*Parody, Satire, Irony, Speech, Babu English, literal translation.*

Introduction:

Nissim Ezekiel was educated in Mumbai and London. A winner of the Sahitya Academy Award, Ezekiel has edited several journals including *Quest and Imprint*. His verse collections are "A Time to Change", "Sixty Poems", "The Third", "The Unfinished Man", "The Exact Name", "Hymns and Darkness". He also has the title Collected plays to his credit. Nissim Ezekiel has emerged as a leader, encouraging new talent in modern Indian English poetry. A poet with professional attitude, his poetry is chiefly introspective and self-analytical and expresses modern concerns in contemporary voice and manner.

Objectives:

Curiosity is a strong motive behind research which adds something new to the treasure of knowledge. Following are some of the basic objectives.

- ➡ To define the term parody.
- ➡ To delineate the concept satire.
- ➡ To study Indianness in the poem.
- ➡ To focus on the use of incorrect grammar.

Methodology:

The methodology for this research paper would be to make a judicious effort from theoretical point of view. The researcher would like to use first hand and second hand material while doing study. Based on the theoretical foundation the researcher aims to justify the need to study of parody with the help of theoretical material. The data for analysis, therefore, comprises of significant works from parody. The study will use primary as well as secondary sources such as Original texts, Theoretical works of critics, Notes Dictionaries, such as Oxford, Cambridge, Webster etc;

Analysis of the poem Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa T.S: A Parody

Nissim Ezekiel thoroughly uses irony, satire, Indianness, parody in his poem, "Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa T.S." A Parody, in current use, is an imitative work created to mock, comment on or trivializes an original work, its subject, author, style, or some other target, by means of humorous, satiric or ironic imitation.

As the literary theorist Linda Hutcheon puts it, "Parody is imitation, not always at the expense of the parodied text."

The writer and critic John Gross observes in his Oxford Book of Parodies, that parody seems to flourish on territory somewhere between pastiche and burlesque.

Parody is one of the most calculated and analytical of literary techniques, it reaches out, by means of subversive mimicry, to any weakness, pretension or lack of self-original in its original.

Hegemon of Thasos was the inventor of a kind parody; by slightly altering the wording in well-known poems he transformed the sublime into the ridiculous. In ancient Greek literature, a parody was a narrative poem imitating the style and prosody of epics but treating light, satirical or mock-heroic subjects.

The title of the poem itself shows Indianness. It is reflected in the use of the initials at the end of the name. The poem is a kind of a farewell speech. A party has been arranged and a number of friends have come to bid send-off to Miss Pushpa T.S. Here I have quoted some lines from the poem.

Friends,

our dear sister

is departing for foreign

in two three days,

(P.125)

The opening lines of the poem are consisted with parody. Here, the poet strictly uses Indianness to describe about Miss Pushpa T.S. Indian speakers use of ‘departing’ in the sense of going or leaving and ‘foreign’ as noun. The language which is used is informal in style. Ezekiel has parodied the babu English spoken by the educated Indian people. One of the features of such English is the use of present continuous tense for the simple present. Ezekiel has done it very carefully and systematically in the poem. For eg. “we are meeting today” for “we meet today”, “I am not remembering” for “I do not remember”, “You are all knowing” for “you all know”, “Miss Pushpa is coming” for “Miss Pushpa come”. Here are numerous examples of babu English. Nissim Ezekiel has parodied faulty use of grammar. For eg. The words “family members” are used for “members of the family”. It is a common like “family doctor”, “family matter”, “family relation”, etc. Here the poet parodied the farewell function too. The poet laughs at the manner of the speaker’s speech.

This poem imitates the idiolect features of English used by Gujarati speakers. Some of these features are also present in other Indian languages: the use of the present progressive tense for the simple present tense, un-English collocation of lexical items, and literal translation of phrases and idioms (R. Parthasarathy, 1976.)

Nissim Ezekiel satirizes certain Indian customs, traditions and manners in the poem Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa T.S. The poet laughs at speaker and his manners of speaking too. The speaker stands for every speaker in Indian context. He uses free and broken language to share the views and emotions of them. The use of language is faulty. The poet mocks at literal translation. For eg. “two three days”, it is literal translation of a vernacular expression. Here is another example of literal translation, “with men also and ladies also”, it is an unacceptable collocation used in literal translation of a vernacular expression. Here is another way of unfolding parody is the way of not using indefinite articles. For eg. “very high family”, “renowned advocate”, here is the absence of the indefinite article ‘a’. The phrase should be like “a very high family”, “a renowned advocate”. Miss Pushpa is laughed at and laughs at all the people.

Nissim Ezekiel is a true English poet in the Indian context. His poem Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa T.S is full of Indianness. One can say it is a very Indian English poem by Nissim Ezekiel. In the poem, the characters and the situations are true in Indian context. The manner of expressing is Indian. For instance.

Pushpa Miss is never saying no.

Whatever I or anybody is asking

She is always saying yes,

(P.126)

Above lines give us an idea about the manner and way of Indian use English in literal translation. The title itself shows Indianness. The title seems to be an imitation and reminds us Harold Pinter's "The Birthday Party". It is an Indian method to write the initials after the name. The use of language is Indian too.

Nissim Ezekiel's poem "Goodbye Party for Miss Pushpa T. S." is a social satire on speech which is delivered on an occasion when we all praise the good nature, helpful and sacrificial attitude, leadership qualities, etc. of the person. It is facilitated on his or her shift to another post, retirement, and so on. In every society such speeches are culture-laden. He describes the internal as well as the external beauty of Miss Pushpa in "Babu Angrezi". He says:

You are all knowing, friends,

what sweetness is in Miss Pushpa.

I don't mean only external sweetness

but internal sweetness.

Miss Pushpa is smiling and smiling

even for no reason

but simply because she is feeling.

(P.126)

